

Synthesis of 5,7,12,14-Tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,7,11,14-tetraene and its Metal Complexes with Chromium-, Nickel-, Cobalt- and Iron(II) Metal Ions

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The tetraaza macrocyclic ligands and their metal complexes have attracted growing interest among the coordination chemists, followed by many works on the metal controlled template and metal-free non-template synthesis of macrocyclic species¹. The amide macrocyclic ligands are of interest because their metal complexes have close resemblance with the porphyrins and corrins in their electronic properties and reactivities. Here, we report the synthesis of a few metal complexes of 5,7,12,14-tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,7,11,14-tetraene [Me₄(14)-tetraene N₄].

[5,7,12,14-Me₄(14)-tetraeneN₄]

Results and Discussion

All the coloured solid complexes (Table 1) are stable at room temperature. The molar conductance values for the complexes using 10⁻³ solution in acetonitrile, DMF and methanol (Table 1) indicates their non-electrolytic and covalent nature. The analytical data show that these macrocyclic complexes can be represented as [M(C₁₄H₂₄N₄)], where M(II) = Ni, Co, Cr and Fe. Molecular weights of these complexes indicate the monomeric nature of the complexes.

The ir spectra of the macrocyclic ligand show a weak band at ~3250 cm⁻¹ which is associated with the N-H stretching mode observed as in metal-free porphyrins². The C-CH₃ and -CH₂- groups present in the ligand are indicated by bands at 1375 and 1425-1435 cm⁻¹ respectively. The characteristic bands due to chelated acetylacetone

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES*

Compd./ (Colour, M.p.C)	Mag. susp. (300 K)	Mol. cond. Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹			Metal% : Found/ (Calcd.)
		DMF	CH ₃ CN	CH ₃ OH	
Ni[Me ₄ (14)-1,3,8,10-tetraene N ₄ (NCS) ₂] ^a	3.08	-	-	-	-
Co[Me ₄ (14)-1,3,8,10-tetraene N ₄ Cl ₂ PF ₆] ^b (Blue-green)	-	-	155	100- 120	-
[Me ₄ (14)-4,7,11,14-tetraene N ₄] (Cream, 98)	Diamag.	-	-	-	-
Ni[Me ₄ (14)-4,7,11,14-tetraene N ₄] (Brown, 140)	Diamag.	39	20	15	18.86 (19.11)
Cr[Me ₄ (14)-4,7,11,14-tetraene N ₄] (Grey, 123)	4.62	42	-	36	18.42 (17.33)
Co[Me ₄ (14)-4,7,11,14-tetraene N ₄] (Brown, 161)	1.82	36	60	52	20.11 (19.19)
Fe[Me ₄ (14)-4,7,11,14-tetraene N ₄] (Brown, 220)	5.30	-	46	-	19.42 (18.36)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses. ^aRefs. 6 and 7. ^bRefs. 7 and 8.

ligand appear at 1570-1500 cm⁻¹. All the complexes show a band around ~1620 cm⁻¹ (C=N)³. At the same time, no band is observed around 1700-1800 cm⁻¹ which indicates the condensation of the amine and the ketone. The bands appearing around 450 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes indicate ν_{M-N} vibration which further confirms the coordination of these groups with the metal ion.

All the complexes show bands at 31500-34000 cm⁻¹ which may be due to charge transfer transitions. The observed magnetic moment values (Table 1) for the Fe^{II} macrocyclic complex and a weak intensity band at 11200-11900 cm⁻¹ region may be assigned to ⁵T_{2g} → ⁵E_g transition which are consistent with the octahedral geometry around Fe^{II} ion. In case of Cr^{II} complex, the observed magnetic moment and electronic spectra showing a weak band at 14700-15400 cm⁻¹ assigned to ⁵E_g → ⁵T_{2g} transitions, are consistent⁴ with the octahedral geometry of Cr^{II} ion.

The cobalt complex shows a band at 13000–14500 cm^{-1} which may be related to the octahedral geometry of the complex around Co^{II} ion. This band corresponds to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}$ transition. A square-planar geometry is suggested for the nickel complex by magnetic moment measurements⁵. The electronic spectra confirms the square-planar geometry which shows two bands at 15000–15900 and 19400–20000 cm^{-1} assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$ transitions respectively. The observed magnetic moment values for all these metal complexes are in close agreement with their electronic spectral data.

The ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectra of the nickel macrocyclic complex show singlets at δ 1.64–2.12 and 2.88–3.32 attributable to CH_3 (12H) protons and the methylene protons (4H) of acetylacetonate moiety respectively. A singlet observed at δ 4.88–5.32 is assigned to methylene protons (8H) adjacent to nitrogen. The shift of the signals towards lower field is an identification of the coordination of the macrocycles.

Experimental

The metal salts used were of B.D.H. make. 1,2-Diaminoethane (ethylenediamine) and acetylacetonate (E. Merck) were used as such.

5,7,12,14-Tetramethyl-1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradeca-4,7,11,14-tetraene (L): The ligand (L) was prepared by dissolving 1,2-diaminoethane (0.05 mol) and acetylacetonate (0.05 mol) in minimum quantity of dry and cold methanol and the solution was refluxed on a water-bath for 3 h at room temperature. It was then concentrated to half of the volume and set aside for two days. The resulting light cream coloured crystals were washed with methanol and ether and dried under reduced pressure.

M[Me₄(14)-tetraene N₄]: The complex was prepared by refluxing an equimolar solution of the ligand (L) and nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate in minimum amount of dry and cold MeOH. The resulting solution was concentrated and dark brown crystals obtained were washed with MeOH and ether under reduced pressure. The nickel complex was found soluble in almost all polar as well as non-polar solvents. Similarly, other things and process remaining the same, cobalt(II) nitrate hexahydrate gave reddish brown solid, soluble in DMF, DMSO, partially soluble in acetone, insoluble in CCl_4 and CHCl_3 ; chromium(II) chloride hexahydrate gave grey coloured solid, soluble in DMF, DMSO and insoluble in acetone, CCl_4 and CHCl_3 ; ferrous chloride (anhydrous) gave light brown solid, soluble in

CH_3CN , benzene, partially soluble in CHCl_3 and insoluble in DMF, DMSO and CCl_4 .

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2100 spectrophotometer, ir spectra (KBr) on a Beckman IR-20 and IR-12 spectrophotometers and ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectra on a Varian F-16 spectrometer. Molecular weight (in methanol) was determined cryoscopically. Magnetic moment was recorded at room temperature on a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM 155 Princeton Applied Research). The VSM was calibrated with a high purity nickel standard showing a saturation moment of 55 emu g^{-1} with a saturation flux 5 kG. C, H and N were estimated microanalytically. The molar conductance was measured using a Systronics 302 conductivity bridge equilibrated at room temperature ($25 \pm 0.01^\circ$).

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References

1. L. F. LINDOY and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1974, **13**, 2495; D. H. BUSCH, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1978, **11**, 392; M. TADOKORO, H. SAKIYAMA, N. MATSUMOTO, M. KODERA, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1992, 313; K. I. MOTODA, H. SAKIYAMA, N. MATSUMOTO, H. OKAWA and S. KIDA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1992, **65**, 1176; M. SHAKIR, S. P. VARKEY and T. A. KHAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1995, **34**, 72; A. W. HERLINGER, E. H. FUNK, R. F. CHORAK, J. W. SIEBERT and E. ROCO, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 69.
2. L. J. BAUCHER and J. J. KATZ, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **89**, 1340.
3. M. S. HOLTZMAN and S. C. CUMMINGS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1976, **15**, 660; W. A. WELSH, G. J. REYNOLDS and P. M. HENRY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **16**, 2558.
4. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1984.
5. M. SHAKIR, S. P. VARKEY and P. S. HAMEED, *J. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **11**, 2964.
6. L. Y. MARTIN, C. R. SPERATI and D. H. BUSCH, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1977, **99**, 2968.
7. G. A. MELSON, "Coordination Chem of Macrocyclic Compounds", Plenum Press, New York, 1979.
8. S. C. JACKELS, K. FARMERY, E. K. BAREFIELD, N. J. ROSE and D. H. BUSCH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1972, **11**, 2893.